

Technical note for “Pharmacist-led services for skin conditions and related physician visits in Ontario”

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Ontario administrative health data sources

In this study we used Ontario's administrative health data holdings, housed at ICES and linked using unique identifiers. We used the following databases:

- **RPDB (Registered Persons Database):** Sociodemographic data for Ontario residents eligible for OHIP health coverage, since March 1991.
- **PCCF (Postal Code Conversion File; Statistics Canada/Canada Post):** Postal code-based geographic linkage, since December 1993.
- **CENSUS (Ontario Census Area Profiles):** Area-level sociodemographic data available at periodic intervals. Used to derive the Ontario Marginalization Index tool (**ON-Marg**) to which the Toronto Community Health Profiles Partnership provides access. We applied the Census cycle closest to the study period (Dec 2020–Dec 2021).
- **DAD (Discharge Abstract Database; Canadian Institute for Health Information [CIHI]):** Inpatient hospitalization records, since March 1988.
- **SDS (Same Day Surgery Database; CIHI):** Same-day surgical procedure records, since March 1991.
- **NACRS (National Ambulatory Care Reporting System; CIHI):** Emergency department and ambulatory care visits, since July 2000.
- **ODB (Ontario Drug Benefit Claims Database):** Public drug claims for eligible Ontarians, including pharmacist-led service claims and associated prescription records, since January 2023 (since the minor ailment program inception date; full ODB Database coverage since March 1990).¹
- **OHIP (Ontario Health Insurance Plan) Claims Database:** Physician billing claims for outpatient services (including outpatient physician visits) provided to Ontarians eligible for the provincial health insurance plan (OHIP), since June 1991.
- **Primary Care Population (PCPOP) Database:** Primary care attachment data, since April 1995.²
- **Ontario College of Pharmacists (OCP) Database:** Pharmacy- and pharmacist-level data, since July 2013.

Study variables, definitions and code lists

Variable	Role	Database	Description																												
Pharmacy service claims³	Population definition	ODB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pharmacist-led services for individuals eligible to receive the publicly funded service from an eligible pharmacy (valid Ontario health insurance number and have not reached the maximum claims per year for the specific condition). Billing claims identified using the following Product Identification Numbers (PINs): <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Skin condition</th> <th>Claim maximum</th> <th>Prescription issued PINs</th> <th>No prescription issued PINs</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>(Mild) Acne</td> <td>4</td> <td>9858248; 9858251</td> <td>9858250; 9858252</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Herpes labialis</td> <td>8</td> <td>9858209; 9858211</td> <td>9858210; 9858212</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dermatitis</td> <td>4</td> <td>9858193; 9858195</td> <td>9858194; 9858196</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Diaper dermatitis</td> <td>4</td> <td>9858257; 9858259</td> <td>9858258; 9858260</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Impetigo</td> <td>2</td> <td>9858213; 9858215</td> <td>9858214; 9858216</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Insect bites and urticaria</td> <td>8</td> <td>9858217; 9858219</td> <td>9858218; 9858220</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Skin condition	Claim maximum	Prescription issued PINs	No prescription issued PINs	(Mild) Acne	4	9858248; 9858251	9858250; 9858252	Herpes labialis	8	9858209; 9858211	9858210; 9858212	Dermatitis	4	9858193; 9858195	9858194; 9858196	Diaper dermatitis	4	9858257; 9858259	9858258; 9858260	Impetigo	2	9858213; 9858215	9858214; 9858216	Insect bites and urticaria	8	9858217; 9858219	9858218; 9858220
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Skin ailments³	Population definition	ODB	<p>6 pharmacist-treatable skin conditions within the program since January 1, 2023:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Mild) acne (added October 1, 2023) Herpes labialis (cold sores) Dermatitis (includes atopic, allergic, contact dermatitis and eczema) Diaper dermatitis (added October 1, 2023) Impetigo Insect bites and urticaria 																												
Resulting prescriptions³	Population definition	ODB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pharmacist-dispensed prescription records linked to pharmacy service claims; first prescription was used to define the cohort. The community pharmacist can issue a prescription or not under the program. Patients assessed but not issued a prescription were excluded from the cohort; they may not have required one, may have been recommended over-the-counter medication or may have been referred for an assessment by a physician). 																												
Physician visit	Outcome	OHIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 1 outpatient visit to any (primary care or specialist) physician within 3 months before or after a first prescription through the pharmacy program for the same skin condition. The OHIP diagnostic codes corresponding to the skin conditions under the minor ailment program were as follows: <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Skin condition</th> <th>Corresponding disease in OHIP</th> <th>OHIP codes</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>(Mild) Acne</td> <td>Acne</td> <td>706</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Herpes labialis</td> <td>Herpes labialis</td> <td>054</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dermatitis</td> <td>Atopic dermatitis Seborrheic dermatitis Contact dermatitis Itch</td> <td>691 690 692 698</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Diaper dermatitis</td> <td>Diaper rash</td> <td>691</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Impetigo</td> <td>Impetigo</td> <td>684</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Insect bites and urticaria</td> <td>Hives (urticaria) Arthropod bites (non-venomous)</td> <td>708 919</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Skin condition	Corresponding disease in OHIP	OHIP codes	(Mild) Acne	Acne	706	Herpes labialis	Herpes labialis	054	Dermatitis	Atopic dermatitis Seborrheic dermatitis Contact dermatitis Itch	691 690 692 698	Diaper dermatitis	Diaper rash	691	Impetigo	Impetigo	684	Insect bites and urticaria	Hives (urticaria) Arthropod bites (non-venomous)	708 919							
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Primary care attachment²	Characteristic	PCPOP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individuals were classified as attached to a primary care provider using a validated algorithm, defined hierarchically as: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> formal enrollment (rostering) to a family physician participating in formal primary care patient enrollment (roster) models; receipt of care at a community health center; or “virtual rostering,” defined as assignment to the physician providing them the plurality of primary care visits over a 2-year period, restricted to physicians with adequate continuity of care. <p>For children younger than 19 years who were not attached after these 3 steps: assignment to a primary care provider using a validated pediatric access algorithm.⁴</p> 																												

Variable	Role	Database	Description
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Otherwise classified as uncertainly attached, rather than unattached, because individuals may still access primary care episodically (eg, walk-in clinic) without ongoing attachment to a primary care provider. • Reason for missingness: not classifiable by algorithm (eg, long-term care residence) and evolving billing code capture. • Sensitivity (90.5%); specificity (46.1%); Positive Predictive Value (PPV, 96.8%).
Sex	Characteristic	RPDB	Biological sex: male or female.
Age	Characteristic	RPDB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calculated from date of birth or estimated as of July 1st of the year of birth. • Categorical: ≤18 years; 19-34 years; 35-64 years; ≥65 years.
Rurality Index for Ontario score⁵⁻⁷	Characteristic	RPDB PCCF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relative rurality ranking, on a 0-100 scale, derived from 3 components of prespecified weights: population count and density (28.6%), travel time to nearest basic referral centre (47.6%), and travel time to nearest advanced referral centre (23.8%). • A higher score reflects higher level of rurality, categorized as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban (score, 0-9); Small town (score, 10-39); Rural (score, ≥40). • Reason for missingness: Missing/invalid postal codes (area-level variable).
Neighborhood income quintiles⁵	Characteristic	RPDB PCCF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on the neighborhood ranking of average household income within each census metropolitan area or census agglomeration linked to participant's best-known residential postal code at the index date. Quintiles 1 (lowest)-5 (highest). • Reason for missingness: Missing/invalid postal codes (area-level variable).
Racialized and newcomer populations quintiles⁸	Characteristic	ON-Marg based on CENSUS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on census data (which uses PCCF). Constitute one of the four dimensions of the Ontario marginalization index. Include measures of high area-level of recent immigrants (in the past 5 years) and those who self-identify as a visible minority (as defined by Statistics Canada). Quintiles 1 (lowest)-5 (highest). • Reason for missingness: Missing/invalid postal codes (area-level variable).
Charlson Comorbidity Index^{9,10}	Characteristic	CIHI (DAD, SDS, NACRS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weighted index of comorbid conditions derived from hospitalization diagnostic codes according to the International Classification of Diseases, 10th revision, Canada (ICD-10-CA); higher index scores indicate greater overall comorbidity burden. • Categorical variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No comorbidity (index, zero); Higher comorbidity (index, ≥1).
Pharmacy claim-volume	Characteristic	OCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defined using the average monthly number of skin-related pharmacy claims under the minor ailment program, calculated as total claims divided by open days, multiplied by 30. • Categorical variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low (≤1 claim/month); Medium (2-4 claims/month); High (≥5 claims/month). • Reason for missingness: Incomplete linkage (eg, pharmacy closure, identifier changes, or pharmacy types not linkable to ODB, such as hospital, central-fill, or private types).
Pharmacy ownership type	Characteristic	OCP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Categorical variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pharmacist owned; Corporate grocery (discount and regular types); Other corporate (big box, small format, and standalone types); Unspecified ownership type.

Abbreviations: CENSUS, Ontario Census Area Profiles; CIHI, Canadian Institute for Health Information; DAD, discharge abstract database; IPDB, ICES physician database; NACRS, National Ambulatory Care Reporting System; OCP, Ontario College of Pharmacists Database; ODB, Ontario Drug Benefit Claims; OHIP, Ontario Health Insurance Plan Claims; ON-Marg, Ontario Marginalization Index; PCCF, Postal Code Conversion File; PCPOP, Primary Care Population Database; PIN, Product Identification Number; RPDB, Registered Persons Database; SDS, Same Day Surgery Database.

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